

COUNTER METRICS

Three types of metric

Usage metrics: Investigations and Requests

Investigations:

- ✓ All user interactions with content
- ✓ Includes interactions with metadata and links
- ✓ Example: video thumbnail

Requests

- ✓ Subset of investigations
- ✓ Interactions with full content only
- ✓ Example: full video

Total Item metrics count all actions

Unique Item metrics deduplicate actions in a session

Unique Title metrics roll up chapter actions to books

SEARCHES

- ✓ **Searches Platform:** search activity across a whole site
- ✓ **Searches Regular:** search activity within a database (user can select a database)
- ✓ **Searches Automated:** search activity within a database (user can't select a database)
- ✓ **Searches Federated:** search activity from outside the platform

DENIALS

- ✓ **No License:** access denied: the content is not licensed for use
- ✓ **Limit Exceeded:** access denied: the cap on the number of users has been exceeded

COUNTER REPORTS

The Reports

Platform Report

- A birds-eye view of usage
- All the metrics

Database Report

- Search is king
- Database-specific

Title Report

- Books and journals
- Usage focused

Item Report

- All the detail
- Great for open access

Standard Views

Book series

TR_B1: Book Requests (Controlled)
TR_B2: Book Access Denied
TR_B3: Book Usage by Access Type

Journal series

TR_J1: Journal Requests (Controlled)
TR_J2: Journal Access Denied
TR_J3: Journal Usage by Access Type
TR_J4: Journal Requests by YOP (Controlled)

prefiltered summaries,
use with care!

PR_P1: Platform Usage

DR_D1: Database Search and Item Usage

DR_D2: Database Access Denied

IR_A1: Journal Article Requests

IR_M1: Multimedia Item Requests

WHICH REPORT SHOULD I USE?

- ✓ We always recommend using one of the four COUNTER Reports
- ✓ The Database and Title Reports offer the best balance of granularity with a usable amount of information
- ✓ The Platform Report is best suited for a birds-eye view of usage
- ✓ The Item Report is excellent for extremely granular data analysis

COUNTER FOR OA

Why measure OA usage?

Return on investment

- ✓ **For subscription content:**
Subscription price ÷ Unique Item Requests = Cost per use
- ✓ **For OA content:**
Article processing charge ÷ Unique Item Requests = Cost per use

Research impact

- ✓ **Citations:** direct interest in content, but take a long time to accrue
- ✓ **Altmetrics:** immediate, but fleeting attention not lasting impact
- ✓ **Usage:** reflects direct interest and accrues immediately – the missing measure of impact!

How to measure OA usage

COUNTER's Global Item Reports are optimised for OA:

- ✓ Standardised method which means your OA metrics are credible and comparable with other publishers worldwide
- ✓ Based on our very granular Item Report, showing usage of each item on a platform.
- ✓ Attribution links usage to institutions – the Global Item report combines attributed usage from every institution with non-attributed usage linked to 'The World'

A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO USING COUNTER

Two formats

JSON

- Machine readable
- Access: COUNTER API

Tabular

- Human readable
- Access: publisher websites

- ✓ Same content, different file format
- ✓ UTF-8 encoding
- ✓ Tabular reports in .tsv to work in any spreadsheet tool

Spreadsheet tools are your friends!

- ✓ Use the COUNTER Reports for maximum flexibility
- ✓ Check out the 'Working with COUNTER Reports in Excel' class
- ✓ Excel has great on-board training and help tools

Filtering

- Rearrange data
- Exclude attributes

Pivot tables

- Rapid summaries
- Visualization

The COUNTER API

- ✓ Find the details on registry.projectcounter.org
- ✓ Log in with your customer id
- ✓ Add the right endpoint...

**Formerly COUNTER
SUSHI**

/status

- Is the SUSHI service active?

/reports

- Which COUNTER Reports are available?

/reports/reportID

- Give me a COUNTER Report!

/members

- Who's in my consortium?

A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO

COUNTER FOR CONSORTIA

Three types of reporting

REQUIRED – Summary reports

- ✓ Aggregated: one report for all members
- ✓ No breakdown by institution
- ✓ Accessed via SUSHI or web interface

REQUIRED – Institutional reports

- ✓ Non-aggregated: separate reports for each member
- ✓ Broken down by default
- ✓ Access through Harvester Tools

OPTIONAL – Detailed reports

- ✓ Aggregated: one report for all members
- ✓ Broken down by institution
- ✓ Accessed via SUSHI or web interface
- ✓ Relies on optional extensions to the Code of Practice

Consortia report caveats

- ✓ Consortium usage reports are for purchased content only, so usage of content purchased separately by members may not appear
- ✓ Where usage can be attributed to multiple consortium members, the consortium reports may show lower usage than the sum of individual institutional reports
- ✓ Consortium members can opt-out of consortium reporting

A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO

COUNTER COMPLIANCE

Count

- User-driven usage
- Valid page requests
- Content items

Exclude

- Robot usage
- Bad page requests
- Non-content records

Delivering reports

- ✓ JSON and tabular formats
- ✓ Month-by-month reporting
- ✓ Available within 4 weeks
- ✓ Year to date PLUS two back years
- ✓ Delivered per customer

Migrating and upgrading

New reporting service, same Release

- ✓ Offer YTD plus two years
- ✓ Try to deliver all data in one report
- ✓ Try to move on the first day of a month

Upgrading to a new Release

- ✓ As above BUT with separate reports
- ✓ Keep offering the older reports for at least three months

Audits

Pre-flight

- Use the Validation Tool

Initiate

- Agree scope
- Brief auditor

Audit

- Auditor tests
- Fixes if needed

Complete

- Audit passed
- Registry updated

Allow plenty of time – audits take at least 3 months

A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO

COUNTER TECH

COUNTER Attributes

Access Type

- Controlled
- Open
- Free To Read

Data Type

- A long list
- Linked to Parent Data Type
- Linked to Components

Access Method

- Regular
- Text and Data Mining

Year of Publication

- 9999 = in press
- 0001 = unknown

Access Types

- ✓ Controlled: Only available to authorized users
- ✓ Open: Available to everyone, with no end date
- ✓ Free To Read: Available to everyone, with an end date

Custom and extended reports

- ✓ Reserved elements (customer details, geographic divisions, content format)
- ✓ Custom values {namespace}:{value}

Host Types: which reports should a platform deliver?

(everyone needs a Platform Report!)

Database Report

- A&I db
- Aggregated Full Content
- Full Content db
- eBook Collection
- Multimedia Collection
- Discovery Service

Title Report

- Aggregated Full Content
- eBook
- eBook Collection
- eJournal

Item Report

- Data Repository
- Multimedia
- Repository
- Scholarly Collaboration Network

A BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO

CHANGES IN R5.1

The Headlines

Still in place

- R5 reports
- R5 metrics

Key changes

- Item as the unit of reporting
- Access Type definitions
- Expanded Data Types
- Upgraded COUNTER API
- Revised JSON

Minor updates

- Registry links in report headers
- Global Item Reports for OA
- Components become optional

Key changes

Item Reporting

- ✓ Like-for-like comparison of usage across different types of content, including in the Item Report
- ✓ Main impact on Item metrics for books and reference works, but the Unique Title metrics are unaffected

COUNTER API

(previously COUNTER SUSHI)

Dropping IP authentication

Updated endpoints

New parameters

JSON

OpenAPI3.1

Deduplicated and compact

Matched to tabular reports

Data types

Longer list to reflect diversity of content

Clarified how to use Parent Data Types

No more Section Types

Components are now optional

Access Types

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